

Measuring Influence on Instagram: A Network-Oblivious Approach - A Reproduction

ExDDS Project - TU Wien

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1 INTRODUCTION

Our objective in this project is to recreate the research paper “Measuring Influence on Instagram: A Network-Oblivious Approach” in which the authors try to identify a method to measure and score the influence of Instagram users [4]. For this, they implement custom features and use regression models to predict the influence score of the users.

The goal of this paper is to assess the reproducibility of the original paper. This paper takes a look at certain aspects regarding reproducibility in scientific research.

2 STRATEGIES

The data with which the results of the original paper are calculated is publicly available¹. As mentioned by the authors, some variables (views, likes, followers) were log-scaled to avoid potential bias towards certain features. Additionally, columns such as likes followers geomean, followers posts ratio, comments likes ratio and focus were added, which the authors calculated based on the original basic features. Furthermore, we reproduced the given plots from the paper using the features.

The models from the original paper were then tried to be reproduced, following the steps that the authors described. Whenever there was uncertainty about exactly what was done originally, necessary steps were implemented to our best knowledge.

The work environment on which the original calculations were made has not been discussed by the authors. In this paper, all results shown are based on calculations done in **R** [5] (version 4.1.1), specifically using the packages `caret` [2] for training and tuning, `elasticnet` [1] for fitting ridge regression models and `ranger` [3] for a fast random forest implementation. Visualization was done with the help of `ggplot2` [6].

The performance metrics the authors decided on in order to assess the models are the coefficient of determination R^2 and Spearman correlation coefficient r_s . In order to determine whether the reproduced results differ significantly from the original results, the reproduced R^2 value was tested against the original value for all models, using a *paired t-test*.

3 PROBLEMS

When reproducing the research paper, several difficulties occurred. The provided dataset had no information about the data acquisition,

¹https://klear.com/sigir/instagram_data.zip

metadata nor a description of the dataset which may be a problem regarding reproducibility. Further, the description of the variables and data used were partially unclear as the authors did not go into detail about how they were exactly created (e.g. focus).

Similarly, there was no exact information given how the mentioned recursive feature elimination was conducted, what variables they used at last and which hyperparameters were tuned in the performed regression models.

Additionally, there seems to be inconsistent use of the transformed variables. The baseline linear regression model seems to be computed using the original values rather than the log-transformed values.

4 COMPARISON OF RESULTS

At first, the plots of the paper were reproducible. Figure 1 shows the distribution of the average views per user on a log-scale and Figures 2, 3 show the views-engagement/follower plot. However, the data provided seems to be different than the data used in the paper. Our analysis yields a mean value of the logarithmed `avg_views` of 745 while the paper reports a value of 748. Nevertheless, this is not a significant difference as a t-test shows ($p = 0.467$).

Figure 1: Histogram of Average Views on Log-Scale

When tuning the regression models it was also not clear which metric was being used to decide on the optimal parameters. It has to be noted that the results were not affected by the tuning metric chosen though, whether the parameters were optimized with respect to R^2 , r_s or even *relative MSE*.

Figure 2: Views vs. Engagements

Figure 3: Views vs. Followers

Table 1 shows our results in comparison with the paper’s results. We ran multiple models per model type (in terms of 10-repeated 5-fold cross-validation) and obtained standard deviations which are helpful for interpreting the numbers.

4.1 Recursive Feature Elimination

The authors mentioned that they used recursive feature elimination (RFE) for generating an informative subset of features for each model. Even so, it was not clear how they applied it in detail such as the usage of cross-validation or evaluation metric.

Furthermore, the variables which ended up in the minimal, reduced models were not given. The authors merely state that they only used half of the features when computing these models.

Using both Ridge regression and random forest approaches for RFE, which was also done in `caret`, we ended up at an acceptable subset of size 2 consisting of `avg_likes` and `avg_followers`. Therefore, in all reduced models we decided to use these two features as the explaining variables.

Table 1: Comparison of Results (Standard Deviations in Parenthesis)

	Regression				Multi-Regression			
	R^2		r_s		R^2		r_s	
	Paper	Our result	Paper	Our result	Paper	Our result	Paper	Our result
full Ridge	0.725	0.788 (0.003)	0.848	0.865 (0.002)	0.727	0.787 (0.005)	0.821	0.865 (0.002)
full RF	0.626	0.821 (0.002)	0.869	0.879 (0.002)	0.621	0.821 (0.002)	0.861	0.879 (0.001)
minimal Ridge	0.723	0.785 (0.003)	0.818	0.862 (0.002)	0.727	0.785 (0.003)	0.818	0.862 (0.002)
minimal RF	0.616	0.774 (0.003)	0.864	0.853 (0.002)	0.611	0.780 (0.003)	0.859	0.860 (0.002)
Followers Baseline	0.211	0.197 (0.307)	0.753	0.753 (0.003)	0.204	0.207 (0.299)	0.725	0.753 (0.003)
Likes Baseline	0.666	0.664 (0.094)	0.859	0.845 (0.002)	0.654	0.666 (0.094)	0.853	0.833 (0.002)

4.2 Ridge Regression

The authors did not provide a description on how the Ridge regression was calculated. Neither the work environment, nor the hyperparameters were given.

Using 5-fold cross validation, repeated 10 times, we trained a Ridge regression model tuning the hyperparameter λ . The obtained model had the parameter $\lambda = 0.01$. It yielded an R^2 of 0.788 as well as a r_s of 0.865. This reproduced value is significantly higher than the original value 0.725 ($p = 0.007$).

In the reduced model, containing only the variables `avg_likes` and `avg_followers`, the optimal value for λ was also found to be $\lambda = 0.01$ yielding R^2 and r_s of 0.785, and 0.862, respectively. This reproduced value is significantly higher than the original value 0.723 ($p = 0.002$) as well.

4.3 Random Forest

Similarly to Ridge regression, no proper information about the number of trees or other tuning parameters were given in the paper. We used the `ranger` package which allows use to tune `mtry` (the number of randomly selected predictors), `splitrule` (the number of the splitrule did not show any proper improvement and hence was set to variance).

The basic random forest yielded an optimal `mtry` of 3 and `min.node.size`=15. Table 1 shows that we achieved much better results in terms of $R^2 = 0.821$ ($p < 0.001$) while the difference in r_s is smaller but yet significant.

In the reduced model, the possible number of different hyperparameters decreases immensely since only 2 features are to be used. Similarly, `splitrule` does not seem to affect the resulting scores by much. The optimal value for the number of randomly selected predictors was found to be `mtry` = 1 while the best result was obtained by `min.node.size` = 15. Again, the difference in R^2 is highly significant ($p < 0.001$).

4.4 Multiple Regression

The authors argue that user statistics of celebrities would show differences compared to those of micro-influencers. In order to solve this problem, they propose a Multiple-Regression model where - based on the follower statistic - the observations are clustered using a K-Means algorithm.

However, the centers of the clusters and hence the number of different clusters are not specified. When trying to reproduce the results, we calculated the Hartigan statistic, as well as the Calinski-Harabasz (CH) statistic for different values of k that were chosen arbitrarily.

Figure 4 shows the Hartigan and the CH-statistic with respect to the number of clusters.

Figure 4: Cluster Statistics for varying values of k

Using the elbow method, we decided to assign each observation to one of 3 clusters. This divides the observations up into users with a high, moderate and low amount of followers, respectively.

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the followers per cluster. It can be seen that the clusters are not overlapping.

Figure 5: Distribution of Followers per Cluster

The authors conclude that using the Multi-Regression approach has not proven useful. As seen in Table 1, the Ridge regression including the clusters yielded - similar to the original paper - nearly equal results compared to the Ridge regression without respect to the clusters.

Running the Ridge regression with respect to the clusters yielded a R^2 value of 0.787. This reproduced value is significantly higher than the original value 0.727 ($p = 0.009$).

The reduced Ridge regression model, containing only the variables `avg_likes`, `avg_followers` as well as the cluster assignment yielded a R^2 value of 0.785. This reproduced value is significantly higher than the original value 0.727 ($p = 0.002$).

In the multiple regression setting for the Random Forest model using all of the features, the same optimal values as in the model

without the clusters were found (`mtry = 3`, `min.node.size = 15`) yielding almost identical, significantly different results ($p < 0.001$). Thus, the comment of authors' that the clustering was not useful is strengthened.

Lastly, in the clustered and reduced setting the optimal values were `mtry = 2` and `min.node.size = 10` which even improves the performance compared to the non-clustered random forest regression approach. Still, we achieve a significantly higher value of R^2 ($p < 0.001$).

4.5 Baselines

The authors use two statistic baselines models, consisting of audience size (`avg_followers`) and engagement level (`avg_likes`) to compare the results with each other. For this, linear regression models were deployed. It was not specified if the baseline models were using log-transformed or original values.

When reproducing the baselines models, we were able to achieve the closest results by using the original base values of the features, which is questionable as they appear to use the log-transformed values for all the other regression models deployed in the paper.

The results were reproduced using the `caret`-library. The evaluation metrics R^2 and r_s were obtained using 5-fold cross-validation using an 80% train-test split. The follower baseline yielded a R^2 of 0.197, which is not significantly different from the original value 0.211 ($p = 0.503$) as well as a r_s of 0.753. The likes baseline yielded a R^2 of 0.664 which is not significantly different from the original value 0.666 ($p = 0.501$) as well as a r_s of 0.845.

Different to the other models the baselines produced a rather high standard deviation for the R^2 with 0.3 for the follower baseline, and 0.09 for the likes baseline. We suspect this is the case as we use non-transformed values for these models, therefore including more skewed data.

Finally, the multiple regression was conducted applying the same method as in chapter 4.4. Again, the results yielded similar values as the original values with a R^2 of 0.204 (original value: 0.204, $p = 0.499$) and a r_s of 0.753 for the follower baseline, and a R^2 of 0.666 (original value: 0.654, $p = 0.493$) and a r_s of 0.833 for the likes baseline. The values were not significantly different than the original values.

5 CONCLUSION

While the origin dataset was provided in the original paper, there was not much more information given. The fact that simple descriptive statistics like the average of the logarithmed views yielded different results has to be questioned, even though this differences are not significant. The work environment was not discussed, no source code was made available and crucial aspects when building the models were left out.

Trying to reproduce the results turned out to be a lot of guesswork because the authors failed to document their workflow well. Specifically, important information which the authors failed to provide include hyperparameters for models, specific information about the process of cross-validation (e.g. was simple or repeated

CV used?) information about how the clustering and the Multi-Regression was calculated as well as information about the recursive feature elimination (how it's done, which variables made the cut, etc.)

Additionally, almost all reproduced results seem to differ significantly compared to the original ones. There is also a huge discrepancy regarding the baselines against which the models were tested. The data suggests that the baselines were calculated using the original values while all models were computed using logarithmic feature values.

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